

Vapor phase acylation of guaiacol with acetic acid over micro, nano and hierarchical

MFI and BEA zeolites

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Abstract

Vapor phase acylation of guaiacol with acetic acid was explored over a series of micro, nanocrystalline, and hierarchical **MFI** and **BEA** zeolites with different acidic and textural properties using a continuous flow reactor. The main products formed over these zeolites were i) guaiacol acetate, which is produced *via* O-acylation; ii) hydroxyacetophenones (HMAPs), which are of pharmaceutical interest and mainly formed by C-acylation of guaiacol and to lesser extent by Fries rearrangement of guaiacol acetate and iii) catechol, which derives from the demethylation/demethoxylation of guaiacol. Both microcrystalline zeolites activity was poor because of the steric/diffusion limitation. Nanocrystalline and hierarchical MFI zeolites with improved accessibility and optimised acid strength and Lewis/Brønsted acid sites ratio were the most suitable catalysts for the continuous production of HMAPs. Although the guaiacol conversion slightly declines along the time on stream, the HMAPs selectivity and yield are enhanced due to deactivation affecting in higher extent to secondary reactions.

1. Introduction

Bio-oils obtained *via* fast pyrolysis of residual lignocellulosic biomass are versatile and renewable precursors of advanced biofuels and chemical building blocks. Although bio-oils are environmentally friendly products, their direct utilisation in either existing petroleum refineries or future bio-refineries still faces numerous technical challenges. [1] Pyrolysis bio-oils have a significantly higher water content (15-30 wt.%) and lower heating values (LHV \approx 17-19 MJ/kg vs 40-45 MJ/kg) than fossil fuels because they consist of reactive oxygenated compounds such as aldehydes, alcohols, carboxylic acids, phenols, furans and lignin oligomers. [1-3] In addition, pyrolysis bio-oils are unstable during their storage and transportation due to repolymerisation reactions, which increase their average molecular weight and viscosity. [3-5] Carboxylic acids, particularly acetic acid, the most abundant single component of pyrolysis bio-oils (up to 25 wt. %), primarily accounts for these undesired reactions during ageing due to the high acidity and corrosiveness of the crude bio-oil. [6-7]

In recent years, catalytic hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) has been considered the most effective route to obtain high-grade fuels derived from pyrolysis bio-oils. However, direct conversion of raw bio-oils into high quality hydrocarbon fuels *via* HDO is hindered by rapid catalyst deactivation *via* coke formation promoted by carboxylic acids. [8-9] Furthermore, full HDO of light carboxylic acids (C₂-C₄) requires high hydrogen consumption and severe reaction conditions, thereby resulting in relatively low-value products such as incondensable alkanes, alcohols or esters. [5,9-12] In particular, HDO of acetic acid eventually produces gases such CH₄ and CO₂, causing significant losses of both carbon and chemical energy in the final bio-fuel. [7] For these reasons, many studies have focused on developing strategies for preparing stable bio-oils using

catalytic processes such as ketonisation or esterification before the hydrotreating treatment, thereby neutralising carboxylic acids by coupling reactions, taking advantage of the cross-reactivity of oxygen-containing functional groups (i.e., alcohols, acids, aldehydes, ketones and phenols, among others). [13-16] However, these approaches have several limitations. Ketonisation can limit the overall carbon efficiency of the process, especially for light carboxylic acids because one mole of CO₂ is released per mole of ketone formed. [10] In catalytic esterification, an external alcohol source, usually light alcohols such as methanol or ethanol, is necessary, and the use of these additives decreases the sustainability of this approach. [14,17]

Direct acylation of phenolic compounds with carboxylic acids to produce hydroxyaromatic ketones, removing oxygen in the form of water, is another, mostly overlooked, alternative for pyrolysis bio-oil valorisation. The resulting hydroxyaromatic ketones can be further converted *via* hydrogenation, directly or after aldol condensation reactions, into hydrocarbons in the gasoline range, thus maintaining the carbon pool in the liquid biofuel. [10,11] In addition, these compounds are high valuable fine chemicals with applications in the cosmetics or pharmaceutical industries. [18-21] For example, ortho- (*o*-HAP) and para-hydroxyacetophenones (*p*-HAP) are widely used to synthesize analgesic or antipyretic drugs. [19] Similarly, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyacetophenone (commercially known as apocynin or acetovallinone) is administered as an anti-asthmatic and therapeutic drug for inflammation-mediated diseases, as well as an adjuvant to antiviral treatments. [22-24] This synthetic approach has a high potential from a green chemistry perspective because conventional procedures applied to obtain these molecules require non-renewable sources of phenolic derivatives and involve using acid chlorides or anhydrides as acylating agents, generating substantial amounts

of waste. In contrast, using carboxylic acids as acylation agents results in the formation of water as the only by-product, which is a less hazardous and more environmentally friendly option. [25-27] However, acetic acid is a poor acylation agent, thus making it more challenging to achieve high yields of HMAPs. [10] Nevertheless, acetic acid can be used not only for the acylation of phenols but also for their coupling with methylfuran, which is another relevant biomass-derived molecule. [28,29]

The acylation of phenolic compounds may proceed through two different pathways: a) O-acylation, yielding the corresponding ester, which can be further transformed into an aromatic ketone via *Fries Rearrangement* or b) direct C-acylation of the aromatic ring or *Friedel-Craft acylation*. Both routes can occur simultaneously, and the extent of each one depends on the acylating agent, on the aromatic substrate, on the reaction conditions (vapor or liquid phase, solvent use, polarity and presence of water, among others) and especially on the acid/base properties of the catalyst itself. Typically, these reactions are catalysed by conventional Lewis acids, including AlCl_3 , TiCl_4 and FeCl_3 . Due to problems associated with the reuse of these homogeneous catalysts, many studies have applied easily recoverable solid catalysts, such as heteropolyacids, mesoporous solids, zeolites or metal oxides. [30-34] For example, Neves and colleagues [26] studied vapor-phase acylation of phenol with acetic acid over the H-ZSM-5 zeolite, obtaining phenyl acetate and o-HAP as the primary products, although O-acylation (esterification) was much faster than C-acylation. In this context, Padró et al. performed vapor-phase acylation of phenol with acetic acid over MCM-41, HPA/MCM-41 mesoporous molecular sieves, HY and HZSM-5 zeolites to assess the effect of structural and acidic properties of catalysts on the yield of the C-acylation reaction. They concluded that phenol acetate formation was mainly promoted by Brønsted acid sites,

whereas phenol C-acylation was favored by the presence of strong Lewis acid sites. Furthermore, phenol acetate can be subsequently converted into o-HAP *via Fries rearrangement*. [18,35] In contrast to phenol with competing O- and C-acylation routes, efficient benzene acetylation with acetic acid over **MFI** to yield acetophenone has been related to strong Brønsted acidity [36], in line with acetic acid coupling with furans. [29] More recently, Resasco's group investigated in detail the liquid phase acylation of various phenolic derivatives with different functionalities (alkoxy- and alkyl-substituted) using acetic acid over several acidic zeolites, reporting that aromatic esters, formed as O-acylation products, are more efficient as acylation agents than acetic acid. [10]

Although Friedel-Crafts acylation of phenol has been extensively investigated, few studies on the acylation of guaiacol -one of the main components of lignin-derived pyrolysis bio-oil - are found in the literature. For instance, this process was studied by Coulthard et al. [37] using glacial acetic acid as acylating agent and $ZnCl_2$ as catalyst, achieving hydroxyacetophenone yields < 4 %. Subsequently, hydroxyacetophenone production was improved *via* guaiacol acylation with acetic or propionic acids in the presence of polyphosphoric acid. [38] To overcome common drawbacks associated with homogeneous catalysts, liquid phase Friedel-Crafts acylation of guaiacol was explored over several solid acids, including modified heteropolyacids (HPA) and modified forms of sulfated zirconia by Yadav et al., in a batch reactor. [39] Vinyl acetate, phenyl acetate, methyl acetate, acetic anhydride and acetic acid were evaluated as acylating agents. More recently, Montañez-Valencia et al. explored the vapor-phase Friedel-Crafts acylation of guaiacol with acetic acid over various acid catalysts based on commercial H-ZSM-5 and H-Beta zeolites and silica modified with heteropolyacids, highlighting the relevance of catalyst acidity for the yield of highly valuable products such as

hydroxyacetophenone. [40] Accordingly, the current study systematically investigates the catalytic behaviour of a series of micro-, nanocrystalline and hierarchical **MFI** and **BEA** zeolites with different morphologies and well-differentiated textural and acidic properties in guaiacol acylation with acetic acid. The catalytic performance of nanocrystalline and hierarchical zeolites has not been previously investigated in this process although the presence of combined micro-mesoporous channel systems and a high share of mesopore/external surface area is expected to have beneficial catalytic effects. More specifically, two microcrystalline zeolites (μ -ZSM-5 and μ -Beta with $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}$ of 15 and 29, respectively), two nanocrystalline samples (n-ZSM-5 and n-Beta with $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}=42$ and 16) and three hierarchical zeolitic materials (two h-ZSM-5 zeolites synthesized with $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}$ of 47 and 62 and a hierarchical Beta zeolite with $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}=42$) have been used as catalysts in this study. Extensive characterisation of the structural and surface properties of the selected materials was performed to assess the key characteristics that affect the catalytic performance of these zeolites.

2. Experimental Section

2.1 Catalyst preparation

a) Synthesis of ZSM-5 zeolites

Two hierarchical ZSM-5 zeolites, with $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}$ of 47 and 62, were prepared using the seed-silanization method, as previously described. [41] Briefly, the precursor solutions, with a molar composition of Al_2O_3 : 80 SiO_2 :11 TPAOH:1500 H_2O and Al_2O_3 : 120 SiO_2 :11 TPAOH:1500 H_2O , were pre-crystallised at 90 °C for 20 h, using a reflux system. Then, a silanization agent, PHAPTMS (phenylaminopropyltrimethoxysilane, Sigma-Aldrich), was added to the pre-crystallised gel in 8 mol% of the total silica content. The solution was stirred under reflux conditions at 90 °C for 6 h. Lastly, the mixture was

crystallised at 170 °C for 7 days in a Teflon-lined stainless-steel reactor under autogenous pressure. The final solid product was filtered, dried and calcined under static air conditions at 550 °C, for 5 h. These samples were denoted as h-ZSM-5 (47) and h-ZSM-5 (62), wherein the number in brackets represent the $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}$ estimated for each material by ICP-OES.

Two commercial ZSM-5 zeolites, supplied by CLARIANT, were also investigated in this study: a microcrystalline ZSM-5 sample, henceforth referred to as μ -ZSM-5 (15), as well as a nanocrystalline zeolite, n-ZSM-5 (42), wherein the number in brackets denotes the $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}$ of each zeolite.

b) *Synthesis of Beta zeolites*

A hierarchical Beta zeolite (denoted as h-Beta (42)) with a Si/Al molar ratio of 42 was prepared following a seed-silanization method described in the literature. [42] Thus, a mixture of fumed silica (Fluka), tetraethylammonium hydroxide (TEAOH 1 M, Alfa-Aesar), aluminium flakes (Sigma-Aldrich) and distilled water was prepared. Then, this solution, with a molar composition of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3:80 \text{ SiO}_2:15.5 \text{ TEAOH}:1000 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$, was pre-crystallised under autogenous pressure at 135 °C for 3 days. The resulting solid was mixed with an aqueous PHAPTMS (Sigma-Aldrich) and TEAOH solution and stirred under reflux conditions at 90 °C, for 6 h. Lastly, crystallisation was performed in a Teflon-lined stainless-steel reactor under autogenous pressure at 170 °C, for 7 days. The final solid product was filtered, dried and calcined under static air conditions at 550 °C, for 5 h.

Similarly, a microcrystalline Beta zeolite with a $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}=29$ was also synthesized following the previously described procedure, albeit omitting the pre-crystallisation and silanization steps (designed as μ -Beta (29)). In addition, a commercial Beta nanozeolite,

provided by Clariant with a Si/Al ratio of 16 (n-Beta (16)), was also investigated in this study after calcination at 550 °C, for 5 h.

2.2. Catalyst Characterisation

XRD patterns were recorded in the range of 5-50° 2θ values on a Philips PW 3040/00 X'Pert diffractometer using Cu Kα radiation operated at 45 kV and 40 mA. Textural properties were determined from Ar adsorption-desorption isotherms measured at 87 K in an Autosorb System (Quantachrom). The specific surface area was calculated using the BET equation, while the total pore volume was determined at a relative pressure of 0.97. The surface corresponding to both micro/mesoporous systems as well as the pore size distribution (PSD) were estimated by applying the NL-DFT model to the adsorption branch of the isotherms, assuming cylindrical geometry. The chemical composition was determined by ICP-OES analysis using a Perkin Elmer Optima 7300AD instrument after acidic digestion of the solid sample. TEM images of the materials were acquired on a PHILIPS TECNAI 20T instrument, working at 200 kV.

The coordination of the aluminium atoms was investigated by ²⁷Al NMR spectroscopy at 104.26 MHz on a VARIAN Infinity 400 spectrometer fitted with a 9.4 T magnet. For spectrum acquisition, the nuclei resonate at 104.26 MHz with a spinning frequency of 4 kHz and at intervals ranging from 5 to 30 s.

The concentration of Brønsted ($C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$) and Lewis (C_{LEWIS}) acid sites was determined after pyridine adsorption followed by FT-IR spectroscopy on a Nicolet 6700 spectrometer with a transmission MCT/B detector. Before the analyses, the samples were pressed into self-supporting wafers (ca. 10 mg cm⁻²) and activated at 450 °C under vacuum for 4 h. Pyridine adsorption was performed at 150 °C for 20 min at a partial pressure of 3.5 Torr. The strength of the acid sites was studied by recording FTIR spectra

after treating the sample at different desorption temperatures (150, 250, 350 and 450 °C) for 20 min. All spectra were recorded with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ by collecting 128 scans for a single spectrum at room temperature. The concentrations of Lewis and Brønsted acid sites were assessed from the integral intensities of bands at 1454 cm⁻¹ (C_{LEWIS}) and at 1545 cm⁻¹ ($C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$). [43]

The total acidity of the fresh and spent catalysts was determined by Temperature Programmed Desorption of Ammonia (NH₃ TPD). Spent catalysts were pre-treated at 120 °C for 24 h to remove solvent molecules retained over the catalyst surface. Initially, ~ 0.1 g of sample was pre-treated under He flow at 600 °C for 1 h. After cooling to 120 °C, the material was saturated by flowing a 10 vol % He/NH₃ mixture for 90 min and, then, flushed with He to remove physically adsorbed NH₃ for 30 min. Lastly, the chemically adsorbed ammonia was determined by increasing the temperature up to 550 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. Ammonia concentration in the evolved stream was monitored using a TCD detector.

2.3. Catalytic tests

Vapor phase acylation of guaiacol with acetic acid was investigated in a fixed-bed laboratory-scale reactor (Microactivity-Reference, PID Eng & Tech) under continuous flow operated at 270 °C at 2 bar of Ar introduced at a rate of 30 mL/min. In these experiments, guaiacol (Alfa Aesar) was dissolved in decalin (Sigma-Aldrich) at a concentration of 3.3 wt.%. Then, the corresponding amount of acetic acid (Sigma-Aldrich) was added for a final [guaiacol/acetic acid]_{MOLAR} ratio of 0.20. The liquid mixture was fed into the reaction system using an HPLC pump (GILSON 307) at a flow rate of 18 ml/h. Before loading the catalyst into the reaction system, 250 mg of catalyst were

pelletised, crushed and sieved to 180 - 250 μm and mixed with silicon carbide to improve the heat transfer and to minimise hot spot effects.

Liquid samples were collected at the reactor outlet using a condenser and a Peltier separator every 30 min. These samples were analysed off-line by gas chromatography. The reaction products were identified using a Bruker GC-MS equipped with a BP-5 column, while quantitative analysis was performed using Agilent, 7890A GC equipped with an Innovax column and a flame ionisation detector (FID). GC was calibrated with commercial standards (SI Table 1). The relative error was lower than 3 %. A detailed description of the calibration procedure is included in Section 2 of Supporting Information. The gas products were collected in sampling bags at 30 min intervals and analysed on a dual channel Agilent® CP-4900 Micro Gas Chromatograph (Micro-GC), equipped with a TCD detector.

Catalytic performance was evaluated regarding guaiacol and acetic acid conversion (X_{GUA} and X_{AA}) and product selectivity respected to guaiacol (S_i), according to the following equations:

$$X_{\text{GUA}}(\%) = \frac{F_{\text{GUA}}^0 - F_{\text{GUA}}}{F_{\text{GUA}}^0} \times 100 \quad [\text{Eq. 1}]$$

$$X_{\text{AA}}(\%) = \frac{F_{\text{AA}}^0 - F_{\text{AA}}}{F_{\text{AA}}^0} \times 100 \quad [\text{Eq. 2}]$$

$$S_i = \frac{F_i}{F_{\text{GUA}}^0 - F_{\text{GUA}}} \times 100 \quad [\text{Eq. 3}]$$

$$\text{Yield}(\%) = \frac{F_i}{F_{\text{GUA}}^0} \times 100 \quad [\text{Eq. 4}]$$

Where F_{GUA}^0 and F_{AA}^0 represent the mole flow of guaiacol and acetic acid in feed, while F_{GUA} and F_{AA} denote the mole flow of both substrates in the outlet stream. F_i is the mole flow of product i in the outlet stream.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterisation of ZSM-5 and Beta zeolites

The Si/Al molar ratios in zeolites, determined by ICP-OES, are included in Table 1. The estimated $[\text{Si}/\text{Al}]_{\text{MOL}}$ of the samples [h-ZSM-5 (47), h-ZSM-5 (62), μ -Beta (29) and h-Beta (42)] were similar to the Si/Al values used in the corresponding synthesis gels.

The XRD patterns of all MFI and BEA zeolites under study confirmed their high crystallinity and phase purity (Fig. 1). The diffraction lines become weaker and wider for hierarchical vs microcrystalline zeolites as the crystalline domains become smaller. [44,45] For MFI samples, different crystal sizes are clearly observed in the TEM images (SI Fig. 1-3). Thus, μ -ZSM-5 (15) is comprised by monocrystalline particles with dimensions of 400 x 100 nm, while n-ZSM-5 (42) is formed by small 30-50 nm nanocrystals. As a result of the agglomeration of these nanocrystals, this latter sample exhibits an interparticle porosity larger than 3 nm (see PSD shown in SI Fig. 4) and a higher contribution of the $S_{\text{MES+EXT}}$ (151 vs 93 m²/g) than that of μ -ZSM-5 (15).

Both hierarchical ZSM-5 zeolites, obtained by the silanization of protozeolitic units, consist of polycrystalline particles formed by ultrasmall zeolitic nanounits (< 10 nm). This morphology derives from the anchoring silanization agent on the zeolite crystal surface, thus hindering the crystal growth by aggregation during the hydrothermal crystallisation treatment. [41,42,46] These zeolitic nanounits exhibit a significant degree of intergrowth. Therefore, adjacent nanounits show the same orientation of the diffraction planes, enabling to distinguish relatively intense peaks in the XRD patterns of these materials. The hindered crystal growth causes a broad mesopore size distribution, centred at 3-4 nm (see NL-DFT PSD shown in SI Fig. 4), derived from the voids evolving between zeolitic nanounits when removing the silanization agent by calcination. Thus, these samples exhibit very high specific surface

areas, reaching values close to 500 m²/g, with a contribution of the S_{MES+EXT} higher than 40 % of the total specific surface area.

The μ -Beta zeolite is formed by particles larger than 400 nm. The particles consist of crystalline domains with diverse orientations (Fig S1-S3), although this structure presents an intrinsically high degree of disorder, which results in wider diffraction peaks. The particle size and shape of the h-Beta sample are similar to those of the microcrystalline material although the presence of small zeolitic moieties is difficult to distinguish by TEM due to the high thickness of the zeolitic particle. Similar to the h-ZSM-5 zeolite, h-Beta has a supermicro/mesoporous system with sizes ranging from 1.5 to 7 nm, resulting from the decrease in crystallite size caused by the silanization agent. [42,46-48] In addition, this sample exhibits very high S_{BET} and S_{MES+EXT}, with values of up to 658 and 226 m²/g, respectively. In n-Beta (16) (a commercial nanozeolite), the presence of different crystalline domains with sizes < 50 nm (SI Fig. 2) results in larger interparticle mesopores (ranging from 3 to 30 nm) than those of h-Beta (42).

The state and coordination of aluminium atoms of both **MFI** and **BEA** zeolites have been studied by ²⁷Al MAS NMR (Fig. 2). All samples exhibit a sharp and intense peak centred at 55 ppm, which corresponds to Al atoms in tetrahedral coordination. In addition, a signal with lower intensity appears at 0 ppm, which is attributed to hexacoordinated aluminium species in non-framework positions. This resonance is more intense in Beta zeolites because of the higher proportion of structural defects typical of BEA structures, thereby decreasing the stability of framework Al atoms upon calcination. [49] Accordingly, the intensity of this signal also rises with the contribution of the S_{MES+EXT} and with the aluminium content of ZSM-5 and Beta zeolitic materials.

The full-width-at-half-maximum (FWHM) value indicates the uniformity of the environment of Al atoms in the zeolite structure (Fig. 2). [49,50] In all cases, the FWHM values were higher in nanocrystalline and hierarchical zeolites than in microcrystalline samples, suggesting that the generation of secondary porosity causes a partial loss of uniformity of the Al environment due to a higher proportion of aluminium atoms in the external surface. Similarly, the FWHM values are higher in Beta zeolites than in both ZSM-5 samples of similar morphology. This is consistent with the higher proportion of the structural defects that are typically present in the **BEA** framework and with the polycrystalline morphology of the zeolitic particles that comprise these materials. [50]

The acidic properties of the catalysts were subjected to NH₃-TPD analysis. The corresponding profiles are shown in Fig. 3, while the overall acidity values are outlined in Table 1. For all samples, two desorption peaks are observed, which denote the presence of medium and strong acid sites. In the profiles of **MFI** zeolites, the desorption peaks are centred at ~200 °C and ~360-390 °C and are more intense in the microcrystalline **MFI** sample due to its higher aluminium content. Accordingly, the overall acidity of μ -MFI is much higher (1.18 mmol NH₃/g) than that exhibited by the nano- and hierarchical **MFI** zeolites (~ 0.28, 0.23 and 0.16 mmol NH₃/g). The lower strength of acid sites in BEA vs MFI zeolite is indicated by the position (~340 °C for μ -Beta; ~290 °C for n-Beta and h-Beta) of the maxima in NH₃-TPD curves. Similar to **MFI** zeolite series, the overall acidity increases with the aluminium amount in a set of **BEA** zeolites. However, the amount of desorbed NH₃ estimated for the n-Beta (15) zeolite is much lower than that calculated for μ -ZSM-5 (16), despite their similar aluminium content.

The concentrations of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites in zeolitic materials were evaluated by pyridine desorption at different temperatures (from 150 to 450 °C) followed by FTIR spectroscopy (see Fig. 4 and Table 1). The overall concentration of Brønsted and Lewis acid sites increases with the aluminium content, in the following order: h-ZSM-5 (62) < h-ZSM-5 (47) < n-ZSM-5 (42) < h-Beta (42) < μ -Beta (29) < μ -ZSM-5 (15) < n-Beta (16). Among **MFI** materials, the microcrystalline μ -ZSM-5 (15), characterized by the highest Al content, has the largest concentration of Brønsted acid sites. The value of $C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$ is significantly lower for n-ZSM-5 (42) and for both hierarchical ZSM-5 samples. In addition, both nano- and hierarchical ZSM-5 exhibit higher Lewis/Brønsted ratios (0.46-0.67) than μ -ZSM-5 (15), with a $C_{\text{LEWIS}}/C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$ of 0.25. These results suggest that the acid sites located over the mesopore/external surface present a different acid site distribution from the internal sites. [47] The concentration of Lewis acid sites is much higher in **BEA** than in **MFI** samples. In particular, the n-Beta (16) zeolite has a significantly lower concentration of Brønsted acid sites than μ -ZSM-5 (15), with a $C_{\text{LEWIS}}/C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$ of 2.09, despite their similar aluminium content. [51] This higher concentration of Lewis acid centres is typically observed for Beta samples and is attributed to the large density of structural defects in the BEA topology. [50]

3.2. Vapor phase acylation of guaiacol with acetic acid over ZSM-5 and Beta zeolites

The catalytic behaviour of micro-, nanocrystalline and hierarchical ZSM-5 and Beta zeolites was investigated in the continuous-flow vapor-phase acylation of guaiacol with acetic acid. This reaction is an attractive route for the synthesis of HMAPs, which are highly valuable compounds for the pharmaceutical and fine chemicals industries. It is widely accepted, that the vapor-phase acylation reaction implies first the activation of

acetic acid to yield the acylium ion, which subsequently attacks the aromatic molecule. [10,18] This process is an electrophilic substitution reaction strongly activated by the hydroxyl and methoxy substituents of the aromatic ring.

Besides targeted HMAPs - the products of guaiacol C-acylation, the formation of additional products was observed under conditions of this study. They include guaiacol acetate (formed due to the contribution of guaiacol O-acylation [40]), catechol (guaiacol demethylation/demethoxylation [52,53]) and the products of its C- and O-acylation (3,4-dihydroxyacetophenone and catechol acetate, respectively). According to the obtained results and previous reports on guaiacol acylation over Friedel-Crafts catalysts (Lewis acids) [37], mineral (Brønsted) acids [54] and in a very recent article exploring commercial zeolites (containing both Brønsted and Lewis acid sites) [40], a plausible reaction scheme over studied hierarchical, micro- and nanocrystalline zeolites is shown in Fig. 5. In addition to C-acylation, the formation of targeted HMAPs via *Fries rearrangement* of guaiacol acetate was considered in Fig. 5 as this path was proven contributing to the formation of aromatic ketones upon acylation of phenolic compounds over zeolites. [10] The extent of guaiacol acetate-to-HMAPs conversion was further estimated under conditions applied in this study.

The occurrence of methylacetate among the products (up to 65 % respect to guaiacol converted moles) suggested a reaction between the acetic acid and methanol generated by guaiacol demethoxylation leading to catechol formation. Indeed, catechol was reported to be formed either due to guaiacol demethylation in a process catalysed by Lewis sites under hydrotreating conditions (salient product CH₄), [52] or demethoxylation promoted by strong Brønsted acids in aqueous solutions (product CH₃OH). [53] The later path obviously prevails in this study due to the absence of H₂ in

the feeding gas. Subsequently, as shown in Fig. 5, catechol acetate can be generated through esterification of this dihydroxylated molecule, while 3,4-dihydroxyacetophenone (DHAP) can be formed through acylation of catechol by acetic acid. Nevertheless, the contribution of demethylation/demethoxylation reaction to the formation of 3,4- dihydroxyacetophenone and catechol acetate could not be excluded and hence was shown in reaction scheme.

In turn, considering the high excess of acetic acid in the reaction media, the contribution of the homogeneous reaction, self-catalysed by acetic acid, can be significant, as previously observed in blends of this carboxylic acid with m-cresol. [10] In the case of guaiacol, this was confirmed elsewhere through a blank test without any heterogeneous catalyst in a batch reactor. [54] Under otherwise similar conditions to those used in the current study, this assay rendered 34 % of guaiacol conversion with nearly 100 % guaiacol acetate selectivity. Accordingly, the continuous flow experiments reported here should also have some contribution of homogeneous esterification, as discussed below.

The evolution of guaiacol conversion with the time-on-stream is illustrated in Fig. 6 for all ZSM-5 and Beta zeolites. For each zeolite topology, **MFI** and **BEA**, guaiacol conversion is higher in materials with enhanced external surface area (nano- and hierarchical zeolites) and improved accessibility of acid sites. The result can be rationalized considering the relatively large kinetic diameter of guaiacol molecule (0.67 nm [56]) hindering its diffusion into the micropores of both **MFI** (the highest pore size is 0.56 nm [57]) and **BEA** (0.67 nm) zeolites where the most of active sites are located. In this way, the highest activity was achieved with h-ZSM-5 (47), although this catalyst presents some deactivation, more markedly at short times on stream. Thus, after 60

minutes, guaiacol conversion is approximately 57.2 %, while this value drops to 39.2 % after 5 h of reaction. A similar behaviour was observed in anisole acylation with acetic anhydride over similar catalysts [58], while deactivation was also significant for acylation of m-cresols with acetic acid. [10] n-ZSM5 (42) shows only a slightly larger conversion (ranging from 53 to 31%) than h-ZSM-5 (62) (ranging from 49.6% at 60 min to 30.1% at 300 min), although these two **MFI** zeolites show a time evolution very similar to that of h-ZSM-5 (47), exhibiting a moderate deactivation. The decline in conversion for these ZSM-5 zeolites was related to the adsorption of reagents/products on the strong acid sites of the catalysts (Fig. 3, vide infra).

In contrast to hierarchical and nanocrystalline **MFI** catalysts with well-exposed external and mesopore surface (Table 1), the guaiacol conversion for sample μ -ZSM-5 (15) is appreciably lower (~18 %) but remains rather constant throughout the catalytic test. In this regard, the catalytic behaviour of this microcrystalline material is more akin to those of Beta zeolites (see Fig. 6, right panel). In the case of the zeolites with a **BEA** topology, those with larger external surface also have higher activity. The initial conversion of guaiacol (~28 %) is very similar over n-Beta (16) and h-Beta (42) but somewhat lower for the last catalyst (25.3 vs 20 % at 300 min, respectively) at a longer time-on-stream, which shows moderate deactivation. Lastly, the activity of μ -Beta (16) is the lowest (X_{GUA} : 9 %) of all the tested zeolites, albeit with only minor variations with time-on-stream.

Acetic acid conversion for the assayed catalysts shows the same ranking observed for guaiacol (see SI Fig. 5), although the values are appreciably lower (20 % at 300 min for the most active h-ZSM-5 (47)). In contrast, except for a small initial decrease, acetic acid conversion does not change appreciably throughout the catalytic tests for any

selected zeolite. Considering the ratio of reagents in the feedstock and the values of guaiacol and acetic acid conversions, approximately 2 molecules of acetic acid are converted by each molecule of guaiacol. However, according to the proposed reaction scheme shown in Fig. 5, only one molecule is added to the main products of the acylation (i.e., guaiacol acetate and HMAPs). The discrepancy between observed and expected consumption of acetic acid suggests that acetic acid is further converted by other routes (i.e., ketonisation, etherification). Acetone is not detected at significant concentrations over any catalysts; thus, ketonisation is apparently irrelevant at the moderate reaction temperature used here. [5] Conversely, the significant methyl acetate production (up to 65 % respect to guaiacol converted moles) suggests a reaction between the acetic acid and methanol generated by guaiacol demethylation/demethoxylation, in line with previous studies on the reactivity of these blends under batch conditions and at moderate temperatures. [54] Furthermore, gas phase analysis identified mainly CO_x, while CH₄, C₂H₄ and C₂H₆ were detected in very low concentrations (< 0.1 wt. % of the initial feed), denoting the lack of any cracking and decomposition activity under the selected reaction conditions for all zeolites under study.

Regarding these results, it is obvious that textural properties have a clear impact on catalytic behaviour of the catalysts tested. Thus, for each zeolite topology, MFI and BEA, guaiacol conversion is higher in materials with enhanced external/mesopore surface area (nano- and hierarchical zeolites), showing that guaiacol accessibility, which is a relatively bulky molecule, is partially hindered in zeolite micropores but favoured on the external/mesopore acid sites. In fact, considering that the contribution of homogeneously catalysed esterification is significant due to the protons provided by the

acetic acid, particularly at low conversions, the catalytic role of microcrystalline zeolites in this reaction seems to be even more limited.

Although the overall acidity is expected to play a key role in these reactions, no clear correlation is found between the concentration of either Lewis or Brønsted acid sites and guaiacol conversion, most likely due to the variable contribution of different pathways of guaiacol transformation, as shown in the tentative reaction network proposed in Fig. 5. However, guaiacol conversion of MFI zeolites are, except for μ -ZSM-5 (15), remarkably higher than for Beta zeolites, although the values of the textural parameters are in the same range for both nano- and hierarchical zeolites (see Table 1). This fact could be related to the enhanced Lewis nature and weaker acid strength of BEA zeolites. [56]

3.3. Product distribution of the acylation of guaiacol over ZSM-5 and Beta zeolites

Distribution of the products formed in guaiacol and acetic acid blend over hierarchical, micro- and nanocrystalline zeolites was further assessed in relation to the structural and acidic characteristics of the catalysts. Firstly, the evolution of selectivity with time-on-stream was compared in Fig. 7 for the hierarchical zeolites h-ZSM-5 (47) and h-Beta (42) with similar aluminium content and textural properties. In addition, the conversions of guaiacol and acetic acid are also included for a more complete view.

At short reaction times, the main product on h-ZSM-5 (47) is catechol (with a selectivity of 41.6 % at 60 min), but significant amounts of catechol acetate (24.2 %) and guaiacol acetate (16.7 %) are simultaneously generated. Furthermore, DHAP (8.8 %) and HMAPs (6.3 %) are also detected at lower concentration in the reaction media, thus highlighting the ability of this catalyst to promote the conversion of bulky molecules. Selectivity towards HMAPs lumps together the production of 4-hydroxy-3-

methoxyacetophenone (apocynin) and 3-hydroxy-3-methoxyacetophenone isomers, although the contribution of the former regioisomer is much higher, that is, approximately 69 % of the total.

Product distribution varies progressively with time-on-stream, and although the selectivity of catechol acetate is basically constant throughout the assay, a remarkable evolution of the yield of other products is observed when using h-ZSM-5 (47) (Fig. 7). Thus, catechol generation (from 41.6 % at 60 min to 22.4 % after 300 min) gradually declines with the increase in guaiacol acetate and HMAPs selectivity (30.3 and 22.4 %, respectively after 300 min). Lastly, DHAP selectivity declines notably after 2 hours on stream, subsequently stabilising at very low values (2 %). As mentioned before, catechol can be produced by guaiacol demethylation/demethoxylation with the formation of methanol, and this reaction is mostly catalysed by strong Brønsted sites located at the external and mesoporous surface of the zeolite. The progressive decrease of the contribution of this route can hardly be due to the increase in the transformation of catechol in other compounds, such as catechol acetate, because the selectivity towards this molecule shows little variation along the catalytic test. In contrast, DHAP production, which requires catechol as intermediate, also decreases with time-on-stream. Accordingly, the partial deactivation of the Brønsted acid sites that promotes guaiacol demethylation/ demethoxylation is the most likely explanation. In fact, guaiacol conversion and catechol selectivity follow a similar trend, suggesting that the deactivated active centres are responsible for catechol formation (acid centres with high strength, as discussed above). Conversely, selectivity to guaiacol acetate and HMAPs shows a nearly 4-fold increase during the same period of continuous processing. This indicates that HMAPs formation is facilitated when the strong acid sites, which promote

catechol formation, are partly deactivated. In addition, DHAP formation *via* HMAPs demethylation/demethoxylation is also inhibited due to the deactivation of strong acid sites, despite the increase in HMAPs selectivity with time-of-stream.

As shown in Fig. 7, h-Beta (42) zeolite exhibits remarkably different catalytic behaviour from h-ZSM-5 (47). As mentioned before, guaiacol conversion is lower for h-Beta (42), while selectivity towards guaiacol acetate is remarkably higher, and further increases with time-on-stream, reaching 96.1 % after 300 minutes. Other products of the reaction are HMAPs, whose production slightly declines with time-on-stream from 11.2 to 5.3%, and traces of catechol acetate and DHAP. These results suggest that the acid sites of h-Beta (42), mostly Lewis acid sites, are not significantly active for the C-acylation of guaiacol and demethoxylation. On the contrary, guaiacol esterification is mainly promoted by the homogeneous catalytic contribution of acetic acid, which acts as a Brønsted catalyst, without participation of the zeolite. The substantial difference in the catalytic behaviour of both h-ZSM-5 (47) and h-Beta (42), with similar aluminium content and textural properties, could be ascribed to the relative proportion of Lewis/Brønsted acid sites, which is 2-fold lower in the **MFI** zeolite ($C_{\text{LEWIS}}/C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}=0.61$ vs 1.12, respectively) and denotes the relevance of Brønsted sites, most likely also in concerted action with Lewis centres. Accordingly, the evolution of product distribution with time-on-stream is similar for n-ZSM-5 (42) and h-ZSM-5 (62) materials with $C_{\text{LEWIS}}/C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}= 0.46$ and 0.67, respectively. Nevertheless, some relevant differences in selectivity are observed between these zeolites (see Fig. 8). Thus, higher HMAPs selectivity is observed after 300 minutes on stream for n-ZSM-5(42) and h-ZSM-5 (62) (ca. 30-33 % in both cases), but at the same time-on-stream, guaiacol acetate production is much higher on the last catalyst (selectivity 16.6 % and 34.8 %, respectively). In turn,

catechol selectivity reaches a maximum value (28.3 %) for n-ZSM-5 (42), while the accessibility of guaiacol is restricted inside the micropores of μ -ZSM-5 (15), whose selectivity towards HMAPs (ranging from 23% at 60 min to 7.5% at 300 min) is limited. In fact, the product distribution is more akin to those of Beta zeolites, and guaiacol acetate is the major product, with a selectivity increasing from 67.8% at 60 min to 92.6% at 300 min, whose formation is mainly homogeneously catalysed by acetic acid.

Although the catalytic behaviour of all Beta zeolites is similar, some variations in selectivity between samples is shown in Fig. 9. Thus, in comparison to h-Beta (42), the contribution of esterification is somewhat lower for n-Beta (16) (83 % selectivity to guaiacol acetate at 300 min), albeit with some catechol (~9.6 - 5.5 %), catechol acetate (~10.6 - 3 %) and HMAPs production (~18 - 6 %). The formation of catechol, catechol acetate and DHAP is reduced because guaiacol and HMAPs demethylation/demethoxylation is promoted by strong Brønsted acid sites, whose concentration is slightly higher for n-Beta (16). Lastly, the behaviour of μ -Beta (15) is different because the selectivity to HMAPs quickly falls from the initial 17 % to virtually zero after 3 hours on stream. Therefore, guaiacol acetate is the only product of the reaction for longer times. This fact suggests a quick deactivation of accessible sites of this microcrystalline zeolite and at longer times on stream, leading to a homogeneously catalysed process.

Considering the relevant contribution of esterification in these catalytic tests, which is homogeneously self-catalysed due to excess of acetic acid, the extent to which this activity may be limited by the competition of chemical equilibrium between guaiacol esterification, to form guaiacol acetate and its decomposition into guaiacol and acetic acid, should be determined, also assessing whether *Fries rearrangement* is a significant pathway to HMAPs formation. For such purposes, a catalytic test was performed over

n-ZSM-5 (42) under the same reaction conditions (270 °C and 2 bar of Ar) using guaiacol acetate as substrate (SI Fig. 6). In this experiment, guaiacol acetate conversion ranged from 17 initially to 4.5 % after 300 minutes on stream. Guaiacol is the major product detected, with selectivity values progressively increasing from 70.0 to 87.6 %. In addition, HMAPs are also detected in this catalytic test at a lower concentration, but its selectivity shows a progressive decline from 30.0 to 8.4%. These results highlight the reversibility of guaiacol acetate formation, which can partly decompose to yield an initial guaiacol and acetic acid blend. In addition, this test confirms that guaiacol acetate could be converted into HMAPs *via Fries rearrangement* over the acid centres of the zeolite, which apparently deactivates gradually over time on stream. [18] However, in contrast to the results reported for the acylation capacity of other aromatic esters, such as m-tolyl acetate, the effectivity of guaiacol acetate for the synthesis of HMAPs is more limited under the current conditions. [10]

For further insight into the variations in catalytic conversion and selectivity during the reaction, NH₃-TPD analyses were additionally performed over the spent catalysts (Fig. 3). After the catalytic tests, a significant decrease in overall acidity values was observed for μ -ZSM-5 (from 1.18 to 0.82 mmol/g), which could be associated with the deactivation of active sites by adsorbed reaction products. This process has been related to the formation of unstable ketenes (CH₂=C=O) from acetyl, eventually resulting in coke deposition. [16,18] The loss of acidity is less significant for n-ZSM-5 and h-ZSM-5 zeolites, owing to their smaller aluminium content and, therefore, moderate initial acidity. Interestingly, for these zeolite catalysts, the decrease in acidity mainly affects the strongest acid sites, those that desorb NH₃ at higher temperatures (~350-390 °C). This modification of the characteristic of the catalyst surface has been related to the

progressive decrease in catechol production and in the parallel increase in HMAPs selectivity. Thus, although the partial deactivation of the strongest acid sites leads to a decrease of the guaiacol conversion (see Fig. 6), it has a favourable effect on the product distribution. Thereby, Fig. 10 represents the evolution of HMAPs yields along the time on stream for nano- and hierarchical ZSM-5 zeolites. It is observed that the HMAPs yield increases along the time on stream, reaching a plateau for about 240 min. Accordingly, the aged catalysts exhibit a better catalytic performance in C-acylation after five hours of time on stream compared to the raw ones in terms of both yield and selectivity towards the target products, and therefore, zeolite regeneration would not be a relevant concern, at least within the range of times on stream studied in this work.

For zeolites Beta, a strong reduction in overall acidity is also observed after the catalytic tests. However, despite this remarkable decrease in the acidity (more than 60 % for μ -Beta), conversion remains constant with time-on-stream for Beta zeolites, indicating that BEA acid centres are not highly active in guaiacol C-acylation. Most likely, these are the centres located inside the micropores, which can interact with acetic acid but are too sterically constrained for bulky molecules.

Based on the above discussed catalytic results, one of the most relevant physicochemical parameters defining selectivity and yield of HMAPs is the acidity of the catalysts. Thus, zeolites with moderate strength of acid centres and a proper balance between Brønsted and Lewis acid sites provide higher yields of HMAPs. These characteristics match those of nanocrystalline and hierarchical ZSM-5 catalysts, while the limited accessibility and the higher acidity of μ -ZSM-5 set this sample apart from the others. In contrast, Beta samples, which have a higher Lewis acidity, are not suitable for C-acylation, as shown graphically in Fig. 11. The higher selectivity towards HMAPs

corresponds to the zeolites with a proportion of Lewis and Brønsted acid sites in the 0.46-0.7 range. These observations highlight the relevance of $C_{\text{LEWIS}}/C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$ for promoting the formation of HMAPs.

Although the substrate and the operational conditions differ significantly, this interpretation is in contrast with the exclusive role of Lewis sites reported for the C-acylation of phenol [18] but consistent with reactivity of other substrates with acetic acid [29,36], which has been related to Brønsted acidity. The findings of this study suggest that a proportion of both Lewis and Brønsted centres must be accessible for promoting the conversion of guaiacol and acetic acid blends, providing nanocrystalline and hierarchical zeolites with a competitive edge thanks to their higher activity. However, Brønsted sites predominate to some extent, which is apparently determinant for HMAPs production.

4. Conclusions

This study explores the catalytic conversion of acetic acid and guaiacol blends using a continuous flow reactor over a number of micro-, nanocrystalline and hierarchical ZSM-5 and Beta zeolites. Both hierarchical and nano- zeolites exhibit improved substrate conversion compared to microcrystalline samples, denoting the importance of active sites accessibility for dealing with the relatively bulky molecules involved in guaiacol acylation. For the samples showing low conversion, as it is the case of microcrystalline ZSM-5 and Beta zeolites, guaiacol acetate is the major product, whose formation is mainly self-catalysed by the presence of an excess of acetic acid. In addition, acidity also has a significant effect on the final product distribution. In this regard, Beta zeolites, with higher ratios of Lewis to Brønsted sites (> 1.0), are more selective to esterification, resulting in higher yields of guaiacol acetate. In contrast, both

nano- and hierarchical ZSM-5 catalysts with a suitable ratio of $C_{\text{LEWIS}}/C_{\text{BRØNSTED}}$ (0.46 – 0.67) show a wider product distribution with HMAPs selectivity higher than 30 % and with a significant production of catechol and catechol acetate. Mild deactivation of these ZSM-5 samples, related to the adsorption of the reaction products on the stronger acidic centres, is observed with time on stream, yielding a progressive decline in catechol production, but with a positive effect due to the parallel increase in both HMAPs yield and selectivity.

These results showed the feasibility of coupling guaiacol and acetic acids to produce valuable chemicals such HMAPs in a continuous process using ZSM-5 zeolites characterized by low Lewis-to-Brønsted acid sites ratios and developed external surface.

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5. References

1. S. Arnold, K. Moss, M. Henkel, R. Hausmann, *Trends in Biotechnology* 35 (10), (2017) 925-936.
2. G. Kabir, B.H. Hameed, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 70 (2017) 945-967.
3. A.V. Bridgwater, *Biomass and Bioenergy* 38 (2012) 68-94.
4. M. Jahirul, M. Rasul, A. Chowdhury, N. Ashwath, *Energies* 5 (2012) 4952-5001.
5. A. Gumidyala, T. Sooknoi, S. Crossley, *Journal of Catalysis* 340 (2016) 76-84.
6. Z. Yang, A. Kumar, R. L. Huhnke, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 50 (2015) 859-870.
7. A. Demirbas, *Fuel Processing Technology*, 88 (2007) 591-597.
8. N. Joshi, A. Lawal, *Chemical Engineering Science* 84 (2012) 761-771.
9. X. Xu, C. Zhang, Y. Liu, Y. Zhai, R. Zhang, *Chemosphere* 93 (2013) 652-660.
10. N.N. Duong, B. Wang, T. Sooknoi, S.P. Crossley, D.E. Resasco, *ChemSusChem* 10 (2017) 2823-2832.
11. J. Feroso, H. Hernando, P. Jana, I. Moreno, J. Přeč, C. Ochoa-Hernández, P. Pizarro, J.M. Coronado, J. Čejka, D.P. Serrano, *Catal. Today* 277 (2016) 171-181.
12. H. Wan, R.V. Chaudhari, B. Subramaniam, *Energy Fuels* 27 (1) (2013) 487-493.
13. D.E. Resasco, *Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* 2 (18) (2011) 2294-2295.
14. M. Milina, S. Mitchell, J. Pérez-Ramírez, *Catalysis Today* 235 (2014) 176-183.
15. T.N. Pham, T. Sooknoi, S. P. Crossley, D.E. Resasco, *ACS Catalysis* 3 (11) (2013) 2456-2473.
16. D.E. Resasco, S.P. Crossley, *Catalysis Today* 257 (2015) 185-199.

17. J.A. Bennett, C.M.A. Parlett, M.A. Isaacs, L.J. Durndell, L. Olivi, A.F. Lee, K. Wilson, *ChemCATChem* 9 (2016) 1648-1654.
18. C.L. Padró, C.R. Apesteguía, *Journal of Catalysis* 226 (2004) 308-320.
19. J.R. Fritch, O.S. Fruchey, T. Horlencko. US Patent 4954652, Hoest Celanese Corporation (1990).
20. I. Uwaydah, M. Aslam, C. Brown, S. Fitzhenry, J. McDonough, US patent 5696274 (1997)
21. J. Climent, A. Corma, S. Iborra, J. Primo, *Journal of Catalysis*, 151 (1995) 60-66.
22. R. Vlahos, J. Stambas, S. Bozinovski, B.R.S. Broughton, G.R. Drummond, S. Selemidis, *PLoS Pathogens* 7 (2011) 1-12.
23. V.F. Ximenes, M.P. Kanegae, S.R. Rissato, M.S. Galhiane, *Archives Biochemical Biophysics*, 457 (2007) 134-141.
24. E.A. Peters, J.T.N. Hiltermann, J. Stolk, *Free Radical Biological Medicine*, 31 (2001), 1442-1447.
25. P. Sommai, O. Kazumi, M. Masahiro, M. Satoni, M. Masakatsu, *Journal of the Chemical Society* 1 (1994) 1703-1707.
26. F. Neves, P. Jayat, G. Magnoux, F.R. Perot, M. Ribeiro, M.G. Guisnet, *Journal of Molecular Catalysis* 93 (1994) 169-179.
27. M. Kawamura, D. M. Cui, T. Hayashi, S. Shimada. *Tetrahedron Letters* 44 (2003) 42, 7715-7717.
28. Y. Jia, J. Pana, P. Dauenhauer, R. J. Gorte *Applied Catalysis A: General* 577 (2019) 107-112.
29. A. Gumidyala, B. Wang, S. Crossley, *Science Advances*, (2016) 2 (9), e1601072.

30. L.A.M. Cardoso, W. Alves, A.R.E. Gonzaga, L.M.G. Aguiar, H.M.C. Andrade, *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical* 209 (2004) 189-197.
31. M.B. Gawande, S.S. Deshpande, S.U. Sonavane, R.V. Jayaram, *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical* 241 (2005) 151-155.
32. M.L. Kantam, K.V. Ranganath, M. Sateesh, K.B.S. Kumar, B.M. Choudary, *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical* 225 (2005) 15-20.
33. M. Ghiaci, R.J. Kalbasi, M. Mollahasani, H. Aghaei. *Applied Catalysis A: General* 320 (2007) 35-42.
34. V.D. Kumari, G. Saroja, A. Ratnamala, M. Noorjahan, M. Subrahmanyam, *Reaction Kinetic, Mechanisms and Catalysis* 79 (2003), 43-51.
35. C.L. Padró, M.E. Sad, C.R. Apesteguía, *Catalysis Today* 116, 2, (2006) 184-190.
36. A.P. Singh, A.K. Pandey, *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical* 123 (1997) 141-147.
37. C.E. Coulthard, J. Marshall, F.L. Pyman, *Journal of the Chemical Society* (1930), 280-291.
38. K. Nakazawa, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 74 (1954), 836-839.
39. G. Yadav, A. Yadav, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 52 (2013), 10627-10636.
40. M.K. Montañez Valencia, C.L. Padró, M.E. Sad, *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 278, 2020, 119317-119330.
41. D.P. Serrano, J. Aguado, J.M. Escola, J.M. Rodríguez, A. Peral, *Chemistry of Materials*, 2006, 18 (10), 2462-2464.
42. J. Aguado, D.P. Serrano, J.M. Rodríguez. *Microporous Mesoporous Materials*, 115 (3) (2008) 504-513.

43. B. Gil, S.I. Zones, S. J. Hwang, M. Bejblová, J. Čejka, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 112 (2008), 2997-3007.
44. B. Adnadjevic, J. Vukicevic, Z. Filipovic-Rojka, V. Markovic, *Zeolites* 12 (1990) 699-702.
45. A.G. Popov, V. S. Pavlovi. I. Ivanova, *Journal of Catalysis* 335, 2016, 155-164.
46. J. Přeč, P. Pizarro, D.P. Serrano, J. Čejka, *Chemical Society Reviews* 47 (2018) 8263-8306.
47. R.A. García-Muñoz, D.P. Serrano, G. Vicente, M. Linares, D. Vitvarova, *Catalysis Today* 243, 141-152.
48. M. Linares, C. Vargas, A. Garcia, C. Ochoa-Hernandez, J. Čejka, R.A. Garcia-Muñoz, D.P. Serrano, *Catalysis Science & Technology* 7 (1), 181-190.
49. E. Oldfield, J. Haase, K.D. Schmitt, S.E. Schramm, *Zeolites* 14 (1994) 101-109.
50. J.C. Jansen, E.J. Creyghton, S.L. Njo, H. van Koningsveld, H. van Bekkum, *Catalysis Today*, 38 (2), (1997) 205-212.
51. V. Rac, V. Rakić, D. Stošić, O. Otman, A. Auroux, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials* 194 (2014) 126-134.
52. E. Laurent, B. Delmon, *Applied Catalysis A: General* 109 (1), (1994), 97-115.
53. L. Yang, W. Zhou, K. Seshan, Y. Li, *Journal of Molecular Catalysis A: Chemical* Volumes 368-369 (2013) 61-65.
54. H. O. Mottern, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1934, 56, 10, 2107–2108.
55. S. Gutiérrez-Rubio, I. Moreno, D.P. Serrano, J.M. Coronado, *ACS Omega* 4 (25), (2019), 21516-21528.
56. H. Lee, H. Kim, M. J. Yu, C. H. Ko, J.K. Jeon, J.Jae, S. H. Park, S. C. Jung, Y. K. Park *Scientific Reports*, 6 (2016) Article number: 28765.

57. <https://europe.iza-structure.org>

58. D.P. Serrano, R.A. García, D. Otero, *Applied Catalysis A: General* 359 (2009) 69-78.

59. X. Wang, S. Zhu, S. Wang, Y. He, Y. Liu, J. Wang, W. Fan, Y. Lv, *RSC Adv.* 9 (2019) 3868-3876.